

<p>Verbal and Non-Verbal Means of Realizing the Conceptual Semantics of “Intensification” in Non-Related Languages</p>		<p>Linguistics</p> <p>Keywords: cognitive typology, macrosemantics of “intensification”, verbalizer, (phoneme, morpheme, lexeme, syntaxeme, phraseological unit, texteme) isomorphic and allomorphic features.</p>
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<p>Abstract</p>		
<p>This article touches upon the six types of the verbalizers of the conceptual macrosemantics of “intensification” established for the first time in Modern English, Uzbek and Russian, which allowed the author to reveal the isomorphic and allomorphic features of the verbalizers and the factors preconditioning the latter. Comparative analysis of the empiric materials of the “intensification” in such typologically different languages as English, Uzbek and Russian shows that there is a solid ground to confirm the universal nature of the conceptual semantics of the “intensification” because of its being a communicatively important phenomenon which may and should be verbalized by the following means in languages: 1) phonemes; 2) morphemes; 3) lexemes; 4) syntaxemes; 5) phraseological units; 6) textemes. All these language units form so called linguoconceptual semantic field of “intensification” in every concrete language, there being the nuclear, dominant, central and peripheral members of the field. The aforementioned typical constituent members of the field represent a certain well organized system of units verbalizing the conceptual semantics of “intensification” on any language. Our analysis has shown that the compared languages are characterized by certain isomorphic and allomorphic features of which the former is explained by the general (universal) laws of development of language as the best means of adequate communication among human beings, whereas the latter (allomorphic features) is accounted for by the original thinking which is accordingly manifested by the specific national verbalizers of the conceptual semantics of “intensification” characterized by idiomatism of their syntax, semantics and pragmatics as well as linguoculturological features. Both features of the intensification in the compared languages are to be taken into consideration while teaching the former at schools, colleges and universities.</p>		

The semantics of “**intensification**” is one of the universal notional categories represented by a concept of “**intensification**” and verbalized by the units of different levels in every concrete language, because “**intensification**” is a communicatively important concept that should by all means be manifested (materialized) or verbalized in any language.

When studying the intensifiers (intensification) in comparison, first of all, we should by all means consider to the definition of the “intensification” as a notional and conceptual semantic category.

Here is the definition formulated from Macmillan English dictionary: “Intensifier – a word that makes the meaning of another word stronger: for example adverbs such as: “very” and “extremely” [8; p.708].

Our analysis of the empiric materials of the “intensification” in such typologically different languages as English, Uzbek and Russian shows that there is a solid ground to confirm the universal nature of the conceptual semantics of the “intensification” because of its being a communicatively important phenomenon which may and should be verbalized by the following means in languages:

1) phonemes: **a) dynamic stress:** *It was ‘utterly im’possible- Буни ‘мутлақо иложиси йўқ – Это ‘абсолютно невозможно!);*

Sometimes specially distinct articulation of words, syllable by syllable, as in ‘Ab-so-‘lu-tly – ‘Аб-‘сол-‘ют-но! – ‘мут-‘ла-‘қо!. б)) **emphatic lengthening of vowels or consonants:** *Yes – ye-e-e-s – жу-у-уда тўғри – пр-а-а-авильно, good – go-o-o-d – жу-у-уда яхши – о-о-чень хорошо; “Just a son of the **oooold** sod”, he went on mirthlessly, “with a tidy little private bank account of – what? Two, three million?” [10; p.147].*

M-m-m-arvellous – из-з-умительный – аж-ж-жойиб; How l-l-ate you are – так п-п-оздно – намунча к-к-еч.

Even a voiceless consonant may be lengthened: ***It’s f-f-filthy!*** – *г-г-грязно – ниҳоятда иф-ф-флос.*

As a rule, vowels are not subject to emphatic lengthening, especially short vowels. This peculiarity of English is a stumbling block to Russian learners, as vowel-lengthening is used freely in Russian for the purpose of creating emphasis: Какой большо-о-й; Да ну-у-у! Не может бы-ы-ыть! [4; p.147].

2) **morphemes:** а) super+noun stem – **supermodel** – **супер**модель - суперколип , **supersoldier**-суперсолдат - супераскар ва х.к.; б) hyper+ noun stem – **hypermarket** (**гипер**маркет – гипербозор) ва х.к. ; в) out+verb stem: outlast (превосходить по длительности – узок чўзилмоқ); outfight (побеждать в бою - жангда ғолиб чиқмоқ) and etc; in uzbek:

1) noun stem+**лар**: Бош**лар**имни қотириб юборяпсан (Мую голову слишком много морочишь - You are racking my brains too much) Ёх-ёх, **юра**қларим куйди, **бўйлар**ингга қоқиндик! (Ох, ох, с-с-сердце горит, лапочка моя! – Oh, oh, the h-h-h-eart is burning, sweetest!);

2) **бе**+noun stem “бенихоя, беҳисоб, беҳад ва х.к.: Мен сиздан беҳад миннатдорман. (Я безогранично /очень, безумно/ благодарен вам - I am endlessly /very, extremely/ grateful for you); 2) verb stem+**мас** (толмас, ўлмас, чарчамас): толмас курашчи (an untiring fighter – неутомимый борец) and etc.

In Russian: а) **супер**-суперхрабрый, суперспособность, суперцена, суперпредложение б)**гипер**:**гипер**звук, **гипер**витаминоз, **гипер**комплексный, **гипер**чувствительный; в) **наи**:**наи**лучший, **наи**больший, **наи**талантливейший, **наи**правейший; г) **пре** - **пре**интересный, **пре**мудрый, **пре**добрейший, **пре**хорошенький, **пре**отличный, **пре**мильный).д). **ультра** - **ультра**модный, **ультра**сов-ременный, **ультра**правый. ж) мега - **мега**тонна, **мега**спора, **мега**фон; з) **пере**- **пере**хитрить, **пере**мерзнуть, **пере**солить, **пере**мудрить; и) **сверх** – **сверх**готовность, **сверх**мощный, **сверх**меткий. **к) об** – обыграть,

These affixes are given into English and Uzbek with the help of intensifying adverbs and degrees of comparison of adjectives:*the best – наилучший - энг яхши; the biggest – наибольший – энг катта; the wisest – премудрый – энг ақлли; the kindest – предобрейший – энг меҳрибон.*

3) Lexemes

1) adjectives:

a) superior: We respect Bill's *superior* knowledge of the area (Биз Биллинг худуд хақида чукур билимини хурмат қиламиз - Мы уважаем Билла за *глубокое* знание об ареале);

б) extreme: The police were accused of using *extreme* violence against the protesters (Полициячилар норози кишиларга нисбатан *ўта* бешафқатликда айбландилар - Полицейские были обвинены в *жестоким* применении силы против протестующих);

в) outstanding: An *outstanding* example of Indian art - *Самый бесценный* образец индийского искусства - Ҳиндистон санъатининг *энг нодир* намунаси);

г) only – You are the *only* person who can help me – (Менга ёрдам бера оладиган *ягона* инсон сизсиз – Вы *единственный* человек, который может помочь мне); *ўзбек тилида: а) ёлғиз (фақат, биргина)*, масалан: **фақат** бир илтимос (**только** одна просьба – **only** one request (**just a** request) and etc;

2) pronouns: *all, every, each, everybody, everything, everyone* and etc: I did *everything* for you (Я для тебя сделал *все* – Мен сен учун *хамманарсани* килдим); He spent his *whole* life in the country (Он провел *всю* свою жизнь в деревне – У ўзининг *бутун* умрини кишлокда ўтказди); in uzbek: *хамма, барча, бари(си), хар бир(и), хар қайси(си), хар ким, хар нарса* and etc: *Ҳамма* хозир далада (*Все* сейчас на поле – *Everybody* is on the field);

3) nouns: *planet, earth, world, life and etc:* How in the world did they make a mistake like that - Как так они могут совершить такую грубую ошибку – Улар қандай қилиб шундай кўпол ҳотога йўл қўйишди экан; He spent *all* his life on the island (Он провел *всю* свою жизнь на острове); in uzbek: *дунё, жаҳон, ер, замин, умр, аср* ва ҳ.к.: Унга бу *дунё* тор (Ему *мир* этот тесен (узок) – *The world* is narrow for him);

4) adverbs: *very, deeply, too, absolutely, astonishingly; extremely;* He came to the meeting *absolutely* late – Он пришел на собрание *абсолютно(совсем)* поздно; in uzbek: *ўта, жуда, энг, роса, бениҳоя, беҳад, бехисоб, чексиз, ниҳоятда, бағоят, доимо, хеч қачон, хеч хам, бир умр, умр бўйи, умри(м)да, хаётда*, масалан: Отанг раҳматлик *умр бўйи* шу ердан жилган эмас эди [13;б.26]. (Your father has spent his *whole life* just here - Твой отец, царство ему небесное, провел *всю* свою *жизнь* только здесь; in uzbek: Болалар *беҳад* қувонишиб, Йўлчининг бўйнига осилишди [12;б.112]. (Будучи *очень* рады, дети бросились в объятие Юлчи – Being *so* happy, the children threw themselves into Yulchy's arms) and etc;

5) numerals: *hundred(s), thousand(s), million(s), billion(s)* “Daddy, we’ve done all this *a thousand times*” [10;р.102] - Дадажон, бу ишни *минг марта* қилганмиз - Дорогой отец, мы эту работу сделали *тысячи раз*; in uzbek: *ўн, юз, минг, миллион*: Тилагимга етказган худога *минг-минг марта* шукур [13;б.48]. (I thank God *a thousand times* for my dreams came true – Я *тысячу раз* благодарен богу за то, что мои мечты сбылись); Менгина эмас, *минг-*

минглаб халқ йиғлади [13;б.114]. (It was not only me who cried, but *thousands* of ordinary folk people also did – Не только я, но и *тысячи* людей заплакали);

6) particles: 1)even, yet, still, just, simply, all (the same), all along, all alone: All the same it was a jolly good show and Cynthia Dark *simply* ripping.

As intensifyingparticle still, yet and the (homonym of definite article) are used with adjectives in comparative degree: 1) The latter place is a very poor town, rendered still poorer in the appearance of its market-place by the ravages of a recent fire. 2) The nearer we drew... themore excited I was to get there, and to run into her arms. Only and but as intensifyingparticle are used with adverbtoo: It was but too true. InUzbek: -ку, ҳам, -у (-ю), -да, -оқ, -ёқ, -ки (-ким): Анча ерни сугорибсизлар- ку, Мироб оналар. Неча марта учрашай дедим- ку, вақтим бўлмади.

In Uzbek language such intensifying particles as: **ахир, ҳатто, ҳаттоки, наҳотки** are actively used:

1. ...тушунтир ахир менга, бир нима дедими... [11; б.47] 2. Солдатга мумкин эмас, албатта, ҳатто уруш вақтида ҳам [11; б.42]. Such words: *тим, лиқ, лим, зирт, қир/шир/қип, зарқ, жиққа* can be used as intensifying particles: 1. Кўчада машиналар қатнови тинган, тим қоронғи ... [11; б.65].

2. Бу ерда ғарқ пишган мевазор боғларнинг хушбўйигина эмас, ...бир чўл ҳиди ҳам димокка ўткир туюлар. **all (the same):** I am sure he's safe, but **all the same**, I wish he'd come homeЯ уверень, он в безопасности, **но всё таки**, хотелось бы, чтобы он пришел домой- Мен ишонаман, у хавфдан холи, **лекин барибир**, мен унинг уйга келишини хоҳлардим.**all /along/:** You've been very nice to me **all along**, (Сиз менга **бир умр** яхши муносабатда бўлдингиз, жаноб Каупервуд – Вы **всю жизнь** были в добрых отношениях со мной, мистер Каупервуд);

3) **all /alone/:** He came through that way **all alone**. [6;p.169] - У бу йўлни **ёлғиз ўзи** босиб ўтди – Он прошел через эту дорогу **сам один**);

4) **syntaxeme:**

a) **phrasemes (word combinations):** on the earth/nothing/nowhere on earth; in the world/not in the world, thousands of pardons, to say a hundred times and etc: Nothing on the earth could get me to speak to her - Хеч қандай инсон зоти мени унга гапиришга мажбур қилолмайди – Никто в этом мире не может заставит меня говорить с ней. In *uzbek:* бир умр, умр бўйи, умри давомида, ер юзида дунё бўйича and etc. У бир умр қўлига газета олмаган эди [7; б.235]. Он в жизни не брал газету в руку – He has never taken a newspaper into his hands;

b) simple sentences:

And she had earth on her hand – У нее вес земной шар был на ладони – Бутун ер шари унинг кафтида турарди; in uzbek; Унда минг паҳлавонинг кучи бор – У него есть сила тысячи богатырей – He has the power of thousands of strong man.

c) compound sentences: There was a smile you can die from – Это была такая улыбка от которой можно с ума сойти – Унинг табассуми шундай гшзал эдики, одам ақлини йўқотиб қўйиши ҳам мумкин эди.

5) phraseological units: *as anything, like anything, like billy-o, under the sun, like mad, like lightning and etc:*

Though he ran like anything, he couldn't catch his train – Хотя он и бежал сломя голову, он все-таки опоздал на поезд – У икки оёғини қўлига олиб югургани билан поедга улгура олмади;

“And they fight”? ... “Like billy-o”, said Paul-Они подрались?- Да ещё как,- ответил Поль – Улар урушдиларми? – Ҳа шундақанги урушдарки, асти қўявер деди Пол;

I am going to miss you a hell of a lot - Я буду по тебе очень-очень скучать – Мен сизни жуда-жуда соғинаман and etc; in uzbek: кулини кўкка совурмоқ/ер билан яқсон қилмоқ/, она суги оғзига келмоқ ва ҳ.к.: Айт, бўлмаса, кулингни кўкка совурамиз! –

Tell the truth, or else we will ruin you! – Скажи правду, иначе мы тебя разорвем на куски!; Бу атласларни Отабойдан ўндиргунча нақ Қўзибойнинг она суги оғзига келди –

It was extremely difficult for Quziboy to persuade Otaboy to give the silk materials – Было ужасно тяжело Кузибаю убедить Атабая дать шелковые материалы).

6) textemes: I have got *a million* things to do before I leave, but I must be there by Monday (Жўнаб кетишимга қадар миллионга қиладиган ишларим бор, лекин душанбагача у ерда бўлишим шарт – У меня *миллион* работ до моего отъезда, но до понедельника я должен быть там). in uzbek: Ҳозир замон шунақа. Пошшолар тахт талашганида *юз мингла* бодам бола-чақаси билан қириб кетганига қарамайди [13;б.15]. (Времена такие сейчас. Когда воюют из-за трона, короли не смотрят на то, что *сотни* тысяч людей со своими детьми истребляются).

All these language units form the so called linguoconceptual semantic field of “intensification” in every concrete language, there being the nuclear, dominant, central and peripheral members of the very field.

The aforementioned typical constituent members of the field represent a certain well organized system of units verbalizing the conceptual semantics of “intensification” in any language.

So all these language units can be called “intenseemes” and their concrete realizations in speech or communication “intensifiers” (like phonemes-phones, morphemes - morphs, etc).

Besides the abovementioned verbal means there are also non-verbal means of expressing the conceptual semantics of “intensification” in communication called “paralinguistic means” (like mimes, expressions of face, nose, lips, eyes, head, a body actions etc.). which will be the object of analysis of another article on the “intensification”.

Having briefly analyzed the verbal and non-verbal means of realizing the conceptual semantics of “intensification” in such typologically different languages as English (with predominantly analytical structure), Uzbek (with agglutinative structure) and Russian (with dominating flective structure), we can conclude that among the three languages under comparison Russian demonstrates more interlevel national means of verbalizing the conceptual semantics of “intensification” than the other two languages subjected to comparative-typological analysis, so it can duely be called the etalon language.

The analysis has shown that the compared languages are characterized by certain isomorphic and allomorphic features of which the former is accounted for by the general(universal) laws of development of language as the best means of adequate communication among human beings. The latter(allomorphic features) is explained by the original thinking(mind) which is accordingly manifested by the specific national verbalizers of the conceptual semantics of “intensification” characterized by idiomatism of their syntax, semantics and pragmatics.

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